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**THE DEPENDENCE OF MILK-PRODUCTIVITY IMPROVEMENT IN
BUSHUEV CATTLE - THE ONLY BREED DEVELOPED IN UZBEKISTAN -
ON THEIR SIRE LINES**

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Abstract

Meeting the growing demand of the population of Uzbekistan for food products calls for the further development of livestock farming. This, in turn, indicates that improving the pedigree value, productivity, fertility and other economically useful traits of farm animals is one of the key tasks facing the sector. It is envisaged that high output will be achieved by preserving the existing cattle population of the republic, increasing its numbers, raising its productivity and improving pedigree-and-selection (breeding) work.

Keywords

Bushuev, breed, cow, line, gene pool, productivity, progeny, milk, pedigree, bull.

Introduction

The adoption of Decree No. PF-6198 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated 1 April 2021, “On the introduction of innovative technologies for expanding the gene pool of livestock breeds and increasing their meat productivity through the application of genetic methods in the field of livestock development, and for broadening the feed base,” provided a strong impetus for the development of animal husbandry in the country and set out measures to improve the system of state governance for the development of scientific and innovative activity. This is of great importance for the further development of livestock farming in Uzbekistan [1]. Cattle

breeding is the leading branch of animal husbandry, and the Bushuev breed is one of the cattle breeds earmarked for rearing on the farms of the republic.

In meeting the population's demand for food products, the bulk of the milk and meat obtained from animal husbandry comes from the cattle-breeding sector. With this in mind, the only dairy breed created in the republic stands out from other cattle breeds owing to a number of economically useful traits: it is adapted to the country's hot, dry climate, resistant to haemoparasitic (blood-parasitic) diseases, consumes and digests local feeds well, and its calves mature rapidly. This breed differs fundamentally from other cattle breeds in several of its biological characteristics, in the high fat content of its milk (4.0% and above), in its heat tolerance and in its adaptability to local conditions [4].

In the development of cattle breeding, the appropriate rearing of young calves and the full-value feeding of heifers and pregnant cows, as well as of cattle fattened for meat, prevent any rise in the cost price of milk and meat products [5]. This measure has a major effect on realising the genetic potential of cows for milk productivity. Today there are more than 1,087 cattle breeds in the world. Among them, the Bushuev breed is the only cultivated breed of Uzbekistan and is regarded as a national asset. As the work of creating this breed was associated with the activity of the agronomist M. M. Bushuev, the breed bears his name.

The pedigree-breeding work to improve the breed was founded at the breeding farm where Bushuev cattle were reared at the experimental field in the Mirzachul (Hungry Steppe), and as a result purebred Bushuev sires were produced. This work intensified further from 1953, when scientists of the Uzbek Research Institute of Animal Husbandry began to study it. In 1957, a State Breeding Enterprise for the rearing of Bushuev cattle was established in the city of Syrdarya. On 8 May 1967, the new productive Bushuev cattle breed was approved as an independent breed.

In this breed, the main part of the body bears a white coat with black—and, in some animals, red—"spots." The calves likewise have a black, and in some cases red, coat. The body is proportionally developed and highly adapted to dry, hot climatic conditions. The breed is resistant to blood-parasitic diseases, has a high fat content in

its milk (4% and above), consumes local feeds well and converts them efficiently into product; its bull-calves have a good dressing yield and produce quality meat [7].

In Bushuev cattle, the head is of medium size; the neck is of medium width and length; the skin is elastic; the withers are of medium width; the back and loin are broad and evenly developed; and the legs are correctly set and strong. The narrowness of the cows' chest and the insufficient development of the udder indicate the importance of pursuing selection work in this direction. The cows' udders are predominantly bowl-shaped, although tub-shaped and rounded forms also occur, and the teats are in most cases cylindrical.

The Bushuev breed was formed within the territory of Syrdarya region. At present, along with the decline in the number of purebred cattle, the milk- and meat-productivity indicators of the cows have fallen sharply. The data show that in recent years the total number of cattle belonging to the Bushuev breed amounted to 13,137 head, of which 37.2% (4,887 head) are purebred and the remaining 62.8% (8,250 head) are crossbreds. Twenty per cent (2,622 head) of all the cattle are reared on farms, and 80% (10,515 head) in private households of the population [2].

According to scientific research, a breed in cattle breeding should comprise 4,500 cows and 150 breeding bulls. Although the number of Bushuev cattle meets the standard requirements, data on productivity and live weight were obtained while implementing the plan of measures for registering the Bushuev breed in Syrdarya region. Feeding the Bushuev breed at the normative level, together with pedigree-breeding work, further increases its productivity.

The Bushuev breed is highly valuable, possessing biological characteristics and economically useful traits such as adaptation to a sharply continental climate; tolerance of heat, cold and dampness; resistance to blood-parasitic diseases; a high content of dry matter in the milk; a high herd-reproduction capacity; a high level of resistance to mastitis and hoof diseases, which have now become widespread among cattle; and undemanding feed requirements [7].

In order to make effective use of the breed's biological characteristics, increasing the number and productivity of Bushuev cattle and improving their selection-and-

breeding traits—drawing on the experience of countries with developed livestock farming in Israel, the USA and Europe, and applying modern biotechnological methods—is a pressing issue that awaits measures at the level of state importance [5].

As part of preserving the gene pool of this breed, the economically useful traits and other biological characteristics of Bushuev cattle selected by phenotypic similarity were studied comparatively at the “Turon ravnaq baraka” pedigree-breeding farm in Syrdarya region, with the aim of establishing new, highly productive herds of Bushuev cattle in the southern regions of the republic.

Selection and mating work is carried out to improve cattle breeds and herds. These two processes form the basis of the science of breeding—namely, the creation and improvement of new animal breeds and the formation of herds of the new gene pool of the Bushuev breed [6].

Selection refers to the separation, at each generation in the rearing of animals, of those animals possessing valuable hereditary qualities and high productivity.

Mating refers to the purposeful pairing of selected male and female animals in order to obtain offspring of even higher quality than the parents. Selection and mating are closely interrelated: the new traits that arise through selection are transmitted to the offspring by means of mating in order to be consolidated.

For the research to be conducted effectively and to a high standard, success depends 25–30% on breed quality (pedigree value), 55–60% on nutritious feeds, and 20–25% on husbandry and on zoohygienic and veterinary-zootechnical requirements.

In our research, the cattle in the experimental groups received full-value feeding and were provided with appropriate housing conditions; they were kept in accordance with zoohygienic and veterinary-zootechnical requirements; the conformation (exterior) indicators of the cows were studied; the milk productivity of the experimental cows was determined; the most productive cows on the experimental farm were assigned to selection groups; and the cows were mated with pedigree bulls [8].

By studying the chemical composition and feed-unit value of the feeds given to the experimental cattle, together with the fodder available on the farm, feeding rations

were developed according to the breed, age, sex and live weight of the cattle and the milk productivity of the cows. Full-value feed types were incorporated into these rations, and an economic effect was obtained. On the farm, all the necessary conditions for keeping the animals have been created in the cattle sheds.

The milk productivity of the Bushuev cows was studied comparatively in the selected experimental group: over the 305 days of the lactation period, the milk yield was recorded every 10 days by means of control milkings. The fat content of the cows' milk was determined once a month using a Lactan analyser; the data obtained were analysed, and the results were substantiated scientifically.

The milk-fat and protein yields of the experimental cows, the milk coefficient and the amount of 4% fat-corrected milk were studied on the basis of the formulas available within the generally accepted methods. The live weight of the experimental animals was determined individually on scales each month, and that of the calved cows from the third month of lactation onward.

The conformation of the experimental animals was assessed by measuring seven body dimensions—withers height, chest width, chest girth, width at the hook (pin) bones, oblique body length, chest depth and cannon-bone girth—and by computing the corresponding indices on their basis [7].

On the experimental farms, a “pedigree nucleus” group and a “bull-producing” group were formed, and new, highly productive herds were established; this is of great importance for preserving the gene pool of the breed.

Cattle breeding is the leading branch of animal husbandry, and the Bushuev breed is one of the cattle breeds earmarked for rearing on the livestock farms of the republic. It is the only dairy breed created in the republic and possesses valuable and important biological and economically useful traits. In the creation of gene-pool herds, the rearing of cattle according to the leading lines is of great scientific and practical importance, since it makes it possible to accelerate the pace at which such herds are formed. This indicates that conducting scientific research in this direction is of pressing importance for preserving the gene pool of the Bushuev cattle breed [3].

In the course of the research, while carrying out rearing work according to the leading lines of the Bushuev breed, three lines of the breed were used in our experiments for the artificial insemination of cows and heifers: the bull Atom-33621 of the Gusar 42 line, the bull Katlovan-55720 of the Rekord 2358 line, and the bull Baron-3 of the Robin 2358 line.

In experimental group I, 10 cows were inseminated with the semen of the bull Atom-33621 of the Gusar 42 line; in experimental group II, 10 cows with the semen of the bull Katlovan-55720 of the Rekord 2358 line; and in experimental group III, 10 first-lactation cows with the semen of the bull Baron-3 of the Robin 2707 line. As a result, healthy calves were obtained from the cows of the experimental groups in the course of the research [7].

Conclusion

As a result of the research, the origin of purebred Bushuev cows and their offspring was studied on the basis of pedigree records; the animals were selected, and their economically useful traits were determined. When the conformation indicators of the young Bushuev animals in the experimental group were studied, the live weight of the cows averaged 463.3 kg, which corresponds to the level required by the breed standard.

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